

BRIEFING PAPER

Isca Evidence, University of Exeter: March 2026

Effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of targeted and population screening for osteoporosis in women: scoping review

Osteoporosis is a bone disease characterised by a deterioration of bone tissue, reduced bone density, and elevated susceptibility to fractures. Post-menopausal women are at particular risk of osteoporosis, and this condition affects more than 3 million UK citizens¹. The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) recommends a strategy of risk assessment in women over and under the age of 65 with risk factors, but there is currently no national screening programme in the UK for osteoporosis² and there is uncertainty that such a programme would be beneficial for health and cost-effectiveness outcomes.

Therefore, we conducted a scoping review to assess evidence for the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of osteoporosis screening in adult women compared with existing care. We also explored equity-related characteristics.

This is a high-level overview of our research to inform decision-making. Further outputs including plain language summaries and academic papers are available:

<https://doi.org/10.3101/GJJT0804>

Key Findings

1. Of **19** included studies, only **3** were **Randomised Controlled Trials (RCTs)** --all of which were conducted in Europe and the UK. **1** of the studies was a **cohort study** that took place in the US.
2. **9** of the included studies **analysed existing data** of the 4 listed above but **addressed outcomes that were not covered** in the original studies. **6** of the included studies were **reviews**.
3. Most of the primary studies **focused on women over the age of 65**. No study included individuals below age 40.
4. The primary studies measured risk of osteoporosis with the **Fracture Risk Assessment Tool (FRAX)** and the **Vertical Fracture Assessment (VFA)** and provided diagnoses using **dual energy x-ray scans (DXA)**.
5. The included reviews addressed **additional outcomes** including **medication use, cost-effectiveness, socio-economic status, and mortality**.
6. Overall, this systematic review highlights the **need for more primary literature** on screening and reveals that **further synthesis of existing evidence is unlikely** to yield more answers.

Over 300,000 people go to hospital for fragility fractures every year¹.

Half of women over age 50 will suffer a fracture due to osteoporosis².

Estimates suggest that the cost to the NHS of treating fragility fractures exceeds £4.7 billion per year³.

Why and how did we do this review?

Review rationale – the ‘why’

1. Fractures resulting from osteoporosis can have a debilitating impact on the lives of those afflicted including pain, reduced mobility, decreased independence, and even death resulting from hip fractures.
2. Additionally, fractures related to osteoporosis are significantly costly for the UK National Health Service (NHS).
3. Recommendations for risk assessment screening is mixed: NICE guidelines recommend opportunistic screening, whilst the UK National Screening Committee (UKNSC) currently recommends against screening. This inconsistency indicates a need for high-quality evidence to inform future recommendations for osteoporosis screening.
4. The impact of equity-related factors such as socio-economic disparities on screening access and effectiveness are not well understood.
5. Through this scoping review, we sought high quality trials and reviews on the effectiveness of screening tools at both the population-level and for targeted screening of women with risk factors for osteoporosis. We evaluated the reported outcomes of screening vs. usual care or no care and examined the impact of equity-related factors on access and utility of screening.

Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement

This review was strengthened by the involvement of a group of around 15 public collaborators, called PERSPEX. This culturally, geographically and demographically diverse group meet monthly, and brought carer, patient, or public perspectives to Isca Evidence: <https://www.exeter.ac.uk/research/groups/medicine/esmi/workstreams/perspex/>.

PERSPEX members discussed our research questions at online meetings hosted across October and November 2024.

Overall, participants preferred to expand the population examined in our review to include more age groups. They were also concerned with outcomes, particularly the potential harms of screening.

The input of PERSPEX members was invaluable to our consideration of a diverse range of perspectives throughout the review process.

Retrieved from <https://storyset.com/online>

Overview of the evidence

Across the bibliographic databases searched, **14,003** references were obtained. After duplicates were removed, **6436** results remained, with 6346 removed after title/abstract screening. The **90 remaining** records were screened at **full text**. Supplementary searching returned a further **821 citations** with **27 screened at full text**. All but 19 articles did not meet our inclusion criteria. Of the **19 articles**, **only 4 contained primary research**, with the rest being either sibling papers or review articles.

What did we find?

Study characteristics

*'Sibling' research refers to studies that analyse existing data in a primary study but may examine additional aspects of the original data.

Overview of findings

Evidence of effectiveness of screening to reduce fractures in women over and under the age of 65
Across the included literature, results were mixed in terms of the efficacy of screening to prevent fractures.

Screening efficacy was measured against fracture incidence for several different types of fractures, including osteoporotic fractures, major osteoporotic fractures, hip fractures, and general all-type fractures.

Evidence of the cost-effectiveness of screening programmes for osteoporosis
Two sibling papers of Shepstone et al. and one review addressed cost-effectiveness as a measure of screening.

The two sibling papers found that screening was both cost-effective and successful in preventing fractures. Only one included review addressed cost effectiveness and observed no benefit of screening in reducing costs associated with osteoporosis.

Consideration of health inequalities in osteoporosis screening research
Very few papers considered the impact of health inequalities on screening. Two sibling papers observed impacts of socioeconomic and education-related factors.

One sibling paper of the Rubin et al. study found that women with higher education were more likely to receive a DXA scan compared to women with only basic education. Another sibling paper for the same study observed that the drop-out rate within a screening programme increased with higher age and lower socioeconomic status.

What are the implications of this review

Screening efficacy was measured for many different types of fractures that can result from osteoporosis –however, conclusions about the effect of screening on the incidence of these fractures is mixed at best. Whilst women over the age of 40 were considered in one review, no study focused on women under 65 years of age. Conclusions for the cost-effectiveness of screening were mixed but promising, with some studies reporting that osteoporosis screening at a targeted level reduced the cost of care. Overall, the studies that met our inclusion criteria were heavily imbalanced with only 4 papers comprising of primary research and the rest contributing no new data but additional analysis.

Limitations and strengths

Our evidence pool was limited by several factors:

- There was a paucity of primary evidence meeting our inclusion criteria, with no new trials in the previous 6 years, so understanding of the impact of osteoporosis screening programmes cannot be significantly advanced.
- The differences between our inclusion criteria and the inclusion criteria used by the reviews we scoped made it difficult to compare findings. But ultimately, all reviews drew on the same handful of trials.

- Our procedure for this scoping review was systematic and transparent –and therefore, replicable.
- We followed best practice guidance and reporting using PRISMA guidelines and involved PERSPEX groups to make sure this research is relevant and applicable to patients and the public.

Future research

The most recent primary research included in this review was published in 2019 and only 4 of the included studies were primary research, whilst the rest were either sibling papers or reviews of existing evidence. This suggests that further evidence synthesis is unlikely to be beneficial without the addition of new primary research that is randomised and high quality. Future research should take care to address the potential harms of screening and the impact of equity-related characteristics on screening such as socioeconomic status.

References

1. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE). *Osteoporosis: assessing the risk of fragility fracture Clinical guideline [CG146]*. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence: 2012. URL: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/cg146/chapter/Recommendations> (accessed 29 August 2025).
2. NHS Inform. *Osteoporosis*. NHS Inform; 2025. URL: <https://www.nhsinform.scot/illnesses-and-conditions/muscle-bone-and-joints/conditions-that-can-affect-multiple-parts-of-the-body/osteoporosis> (accessed 29 August 2025).
3. Gregson CL, Armstrong DJ, Bowden J, Cooper C, Edwards J, Gittoes NJL, et.al. UK clinical guidance for the prevention and treatment of osteoporosis. *Archives of Osteoporosis* 2022;**17**:58. https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8979902/pdf/11657_2022_Article_1061.pdf
4. Becker K, Weiland M, Febrey S, Nunns M, Buckland J, Abbot R, Whear R, Bethel A, Shaw E, Boddy K, Melendez-Torres G.J., Thompson Coon, J. Effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of targeted and population screening for osteoporosis in women: scoping review.

View our full report here:

Contact Us

Isca Evidence
South Cloisters
St Lukes Campus
University of Exeter
EX1 2LU

IscaEvidence@exeter.ac.uk

Find and follow Isca Evidence on [LinkedIn](#)

Isca Evidence

We are one of 13 research groups in the UK commissioned by the National Institute for Health and Care Research [Evidence Synthesis Programme](#) to address knowledge gaps or to answer a specific need for health, public health and social care audiences.